

IMPROVED EFFECTIVENESS IN TREATING PATIENTS WITH ASCITS PERITONITIS CAN BE ACHIEVED THROUGH THE CREATION OF AN ERGONOMIC ANTIBIOTIC THERAPY PROGRAM.

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Relevance: A small intestine motility abnormality brought on by cirrhosis increases the risk of intestinal bacterial overgrowth and translocation. Furthermore, the fact that these patients use proton pump inhibitors often may make this problem worse by decreasing stomach acidity and increasing intestinal permeability, which encourages bacterial translocation and colonization of mesenteric lymph nodes. The deterioration of the body's defensive mechanisms also contributes to the subsequent infection of the fluid in the peritoneal cavity. Additionally, bacteria that cause SBP can enter the peritoneal cavity through the lymphatic or circulatory systems from extra-gastrointestinal foci such the lungs, the urinary tract, dermatitis and subcutaneous tissue, pharyngitis, and frequently disregarded odontogenic foci.

The diagnosis confirms the finding of > 250 polymorphonuclear cells (PMNs) in a milliliter of ascitic fluid. If additionally the ascitic fluid culture is positive, as is observed in approximately 40% of SBP cases, we can diagnose a culture-positive SBP; otherwise the disease is called neutrocytic ascites. When the ascitic fluid culture is positive and the number of PMNs is < 250 in a milliliter of ascitic fluid the condition is called bacterascites. As cirrhosis is a condition of immunosuppression, called cirrhosis-associated immune dysfunction (CAID), the body's response to infection may be poorly expressed. Therefore, in all patients with liver cirrhosis and even mild ascites, in the case of sudden deterioration of liver function, SBP should always be taken into account, even in the absence of obvious clinical symptoms or deviations in laboratory tests.

We discuss the pathogenesis, diagnosis, and current clinical management of ascites, with an emphasis on recent promising developments such as closed transjugular intrahepatic portosystemic shunt. Spontaneous bacterial peritonitis occurs in up to 10% of patients with ascites due to bacterial overgrowth with translocation through increased permeability of the small intestinal wall and disruption of protective mechanisms. Against the background of AP, liver failure with nephrotic syndrome increases in 30% of patients.

Primary ascites-peritonitis, or, according to foreign literature, spontaneous bacterial peritonitis, causes difficulties in diagnosis. The cause of spontaneous bacterial AP is the penetration of microorganisms through the intestinal wall into the mesenteric lymph nodes and the peritoneal cavity.

Secondary AP in patients with cirrhosis occurs due to inflammatory processes in the abdominal cavity and pelvis, perforation of hollow organs, strangulated hernias, and surgical interventions. The effectiveness of treatment for AP largely depends on its early diagnosis. According to the literature, today diagnostic paracentesis with laboratory testing of AF is of decisive importance. Determination of the number of polymorphonuclear leukocytes, protein content, albumin and amylase concentrations is considered mandatory.

Objective Of The Study — The effectiveness of treatment of patients with AP can be improved by substantiating the optimal antibiotic therapy program in combination with complex treatment of patients with cirrhosis.

Materials And Methods The results of treatment of 23 patients with cirrhosis complicated by AP were analyzed. There were 10 men (43.5%), 13 women (56.5%). The average age was 57.5 ± 11.4 years. According to the degree of hepatic decompensation in accordance with the Child – Turcotte – Pugh criteria, patients were distributed as follows: class B - 3 patients, class C - 20 patients. According to the nature of ascites, 8 patients had transient ascites, and 15 patients had resistant ascites.

Primary ascites-peritonitis was diagnosed in 16 patients. Secondary bacterial peritonitis was detected in 7 patients: in 2 patients - as a consequence of gangrenous calculous cholecystitis, in 1 - phlegmonous appendicitis. Four patients diagnosed with secondary bacterial peritonitis had a history of invasive manipulations accompanied by a violation of the integrity of the peritoneum: laparocentesis in 2 patients, mesentericocaval-H anastomosis in one case, and herneoplasty for an umbilical hernia in one case.

All patients underwent puncture of the peritoneal cavity under ultrasound guidance. In 11 (52.3%) patients, ultrasound of the abdominal cavity revealed acoustic heterogeneity of the AF: floating fibrin threads, suspended protein particles, and fibrinous deposits were visualized. However, their presence was not strictly pathognomonic for AP.

The diagnosis of ascites-peritonitis was established when the total cytosis in the AF increased over 800 cells in 1 μ l and the number of neutrophil leukocytes increased over 250 cells in 1 μ l. To exclude infection of the AF, in

each case, its bacteriological control was carried out by inoculating it on enrichment media.

Results Of The Study showed that the maximum concentration of cefoperazone and sulbactam when administered intravenously is detected 1 hour after intravenous administration of the drug and decreases by 37% by 12 hours. The dynamics of drug concentrations in the AF were of a different nature: Cmax in the AF reached values of $24.097 \pm 3.375 \mu\text{g/ml}$ 1 hour after the start of intravenous administration and decreased by half by 12 hours from the initial level.

When comparing the concentrations of the antibacterial drug in the AF, it was revealed that the concentration of cefoperazone and sulbactam in the second group after 1 hour was significantly lower, but by 6 and 12 hours it increased significantly and exceeded by 64% the concentration in the AF of the first group.

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With endolymphatic administration of the antibiotic, its bioavailability in ascitic fluid is significantly higher than with intravenous administration. However, the effective concentration is achieved only 6 hours after administration. When administered intravenously, within an hour the concentration of cefoperazone is significantly higher ($24.097 \pm 3.375 \mu\text{g/ml}$).

Taking into account the obtained data on the bioavailability of cefbactam in the AF, 3 patients of the third group received combination antibacterial therapy. After the diagnosis of AP was made, antibacterial therapy was started with intravenous administration. Then, after inserting a catheter into the inguinal lymph node, cefbactam at a dose of 1 gram was administered endolymphatically. A study of the concentration of cefoperazone and sulbactam in AF was carried out .

With combined antibacterial treatment, the effect of the antibiotic began from the first hours of the start of therapy and persisted for 12 hours. On the 2nd day after the start of antibacterial therapy, all patients underwent repeated cytological and microbiological examination of the AF.

Conclusions When diagnosing AP, it is necessary to begin timely combination antibacterial therapy. It should include joint, simultaneous intravenous and endolymphatic administration of cefbactam.

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